

Deliverable D5.3b

Hot Spot detection through wastewater surveillance and samples data collection

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1. Executive Summary

1.1 Deliverable Scope

The deliverable aims to provide a research response to the fight against the COVID outbreak with the early detection of epidemic hotspots caused by the spread of SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern.

1.2 Work accomplished

We actively participated and supported European initiatives aimed at the implementation of standardised methods for the quantification and sequencing of viral genomes from wastewater samples, at the collection and reporting of wastewater epidemiology data in a timely manner through national and European dedicated dashboards and/or websites, such as the Italian National Dashboard/Wastewater Bulletin¹ and the JRC's Digital European Exchange Platform² and Elixir through the COVID-19 Data Portal³ and contributed to the development of the Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk)⁴ to build on tools and methods and to ensure data quality in wastewater surveillance⁵

1.3 Conclusion

With this work, we were able to contribute to the implementation of wastewater surveillance for the early detection of epidemic hotspots. The need for harmonisation, standardisation and harmonisation of laboratory methods and metadata has emerged in order to ensure interoperability of data and information exchange across borders to drive public health measures.

By providing support to the standardisation and quality control of wastewater surveillance methods having contributed to the Infectious Diseases Tool kit section on “Pathogen Characterization - Quality Control”, we have provided guidance for sample handling procedures which is crucial for production of quality data.

¹ Wastewater Bulletin: <https://www.iss.it/cov19-acque-reflue>

² JRC's Digital European Exchange Platform: <https://wastewater-observatory.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#/>

³ ELIXIR COVID19 Wastewater Surveillance Working Group:
<https://www.covid19dataportal.org/partners?activeTab=Working%20groups>

⁴ Infectious Diseases Toolkit: <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

⁵ Infectious Diseases Toolkit - Pathogen characterisation:
<https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/pathogen-characterisation/quality-control>

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal.	No
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	Yes
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	No
	4. Engagement to stakeholders (RI, national centres, policymakers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	No
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	No
	3. Demonstrate transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries, and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve epidemiology and public health research needs.	Yes
	4. Demonstrate assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the ongoing European VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	No

<p>Objective 3</p> <p>Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19</p>	<p>1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility and disease pathways.</p> <p>2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease sources based on mappings across sources and research domains.</p> <p>3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant sources.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>No</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern</p>	<p>1. Broad uptake of viral <i>Data Hubs</i> across Europe delivers an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.</p> <p>2. Infrastructure and quality workflows are mobilised and shared to produce open, normative variant data incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision-making.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>No</p>
<p>Objective 5</p> <p>Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and European Health Data Space (EHDS)</p>	<p>1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on the work of other guideline-producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).</p> <p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	<p>No</p> <p>Yes</p>

	3. Alignment (policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.	No
	4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps and to exchange experiences and knowledge.	No

3. Methods

3.1 Deliverable scope

The deliverable aims to provide a research response to the fight against the COVID outbreak with the early detection of epidemic hotspots caused by the spread of SARS-CoV-2 variants of concern.

3.1.1 Relationship with other WPs

- **WP4:** Rafael Buono (Elixir), Eva Garcia Alvarez (BBMRI-ERIC), Stian Soiland-Reyes (University of Manchester)
Development of the Infectious Diseases Toolkit with methods and to ensure data quality in wastewater surveillance⁶

3.2 Methodology

Quantitative analysis of SARS-CoV2 viral g variants genomic sequences in urban wastewater samples from Lombardy Region has been described in <https://www.iss.it/cov19-acque-reflue>

Evaluation of pre-analytical and analytical methods for detecting SARS-CoV-2 in municipal wastewater samples in northern Italy has been described in <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14050833>.

Tools and methods to ensure data quality in wastewater surveillance are described in the Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk)⁷.

Standardisation of sample collection, transport, preanalytical and analytical processing of samples used for viral detection and characterization has been described in <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/pathogen-characterisation/quality-control>

⁶ Infectious Diseases Toolkit - Pathogen characterisation:
<https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/pathogen-characterisation/quality-control>

⁷ Infectious Diseases Toolkit: <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Introduction

Microbes proliferate rapidly, mutate frequently, and adapt with relative ease to new environments and hosts. This results in a dynamic and constantly evolving microbial world allowing the emergence of new human infectious diseases with pandemic potential¹. Furthermore, the emergence of new pathogens is being increasingly driven by intensified land use, environmental degradation, and urbanisation and further enhanced by significant economic and social inequalities, climate changes, and increased global connections². Such pandemic potential has been demonstrated by the recent coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, which resulted in approximately 14.9 million deaths worldwide in 2020-2021⁸.

The increasing awareness of the pandemic potential of emerging pathogens has emphasised the need and central role of infectious disease surveillance in informing preventative, containment, mitigation, and suppression measures as well as the availability for research of data from multiple domains, sources, and countries to allow research. Numerous data resources already exist, but identifying, connecting, and integrating these for effective analysis remains a major challenge.

As a result the WHO Independent Panel⁴ has promoted a call for action on pandemic preparedness aiming to *“establish a new global system for surveillance, based on full transparency by all parties, using state-of-the-art digital tools to connect information centres around the world and including animal and environmental health surveillance, with appropriate protections of people’s rights”*.

In particular, an effective pandemic preparedness surveillance system needs to pay particular attention to geographical epidemic ‘hotspots’ for the detection in real time of circulating pathogens in order to anticipate and interrupt the consequence of epidemics and pandemics events by driving public health measures to contain their local diffusion⁵. This involves collecting and analysing data about pathogens in wildlife, environmental sources and/or humans in ways that are sufficiently rapid for the early identification of such epidemic ‘hotspots’. Furthermore, an important component of this early warning system is the potential for microbial genome sequencing to determine the emergence of new variants.

The identification of epidemic ‘hotspots’ therefore serve as an effective model of pandemic preparedness, with an important public health impact in allowing preventative measures as well as surveillance-informed public health interventions aimed at the containment and elimination of the epidemic event⁵.

To prepare for future outbreaks, it is also imperative to mobilise -omic data for reuse, across country boundaries, disciplines and technologies, to study the molecular mechanisms of SARS-CoV-2 and to move beyond the current COVID-19 pandemic.

⁸ WHO News Release 5 May 2022:

<https://www.who.int/news/item/05-05-2022-14.9-million-excess-deaths-were-associated-with-the-covid-19-pandemic-in-2020-and-2021>

4.2 Early Detection of Epidemic Hotspots

We explored methods and models used for viral monitoring in wastewater samples and we identified the needs for the implementation of this strategy in response to the COVID-19 Pandemic:

- a) the need for the standardisation of laboratory methods for the quantification and sequencing of viral genomes and the definition of multiple parameters influencing SARS-CoV2 RNA concentrations in wastewater, such as the catchment size, air temperature, wastewater flow rate, sampling technique and frequency;
- b) the requirement for improved standardisation and harmonisation of metadata collection, and data sharing;
- c) the ELSI aspects related to managing wastewater data as well as GDPR compliance.

For this purpose, we participated in national and international initiatives on wastewater surveillance for the early detection of epidemic hotspots. This work has provided insights on its implementation and collection of data for the Epidemic Hotspot use-case.

- I. The Italian SARI (**S**orveglianza **A**mbientale **R**eflue in **I**talia) Project. In this project we participated in the monitoring and quantification of the presence of SARS-COV-2 viral variants genomic sequences in wastewater over the whole national territory. The National Institute of Health (ISS) coordinated the standardisation of laboratory protocols, the quality assurance assessment of laboratory results and metadata collection on the quantification of SARS-CoV2 sequences through the development of a National Dashboard. A total of 167 Wastewater Treatment Plants located in urban centres throughout Italy have been involved in the project for the collection of wastewaters. Data from approximately 200 samples per week are uploaded on the National DashBoard within 48 hours from sample collection⁹. We actively participated to this national project, taking part to the Lombardy Regional Wastewater Surveillance Network, by weekly performing the quantitative analysis of SARS-CoV2 viral genomes in urban wastewater samples and by monthly providing nucleic acid extracts of these samples to ISS for SARS-CoV2 sequence analysis, to assess the emergence and diffusion of new viral variants. We also evaluated the performance of different pre-analytical and analytical methods for identifying the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in untreated municipal wastewaters samples by conducting an inter-laboratory proficiency test and defined a new pre-analytical and analytical workflow to detect SARS-CoV-2 from wastewater samples that was implemented in the framework of the laboratories' network in the Lombardy Region¹⁰.

⁹ <https://www.iss.it/cov19-acque-reflue>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.3390/w14050833>

Wastewater Treatment Plants sampling points: 167 throughout Italy

The size of each dot is scaled on the population equivalent of the WTP

Quiver graph representing Sars-Cov-2 trends in wastewater in Italy in the period 1 October 2021 to 31 March 2022 (Top) and trends in COVID-19 cases (Bottom).

- II. The EU Sewage Sentinel System for SARS-CoV-2 and the Digital European Exchange Platform (EU4S-DEEP), coordinated by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre. This is a framework and a web-based platform set up as a digital epidemic surveillance and management system, based on combining non-invasive virus detection methods in large populations. The system provide effective science-based and informed decision-support throughout the entire epidemic management cycle, i.e., mitigation, preparedness, response and recovery, including the investigation of various what-if scenarios for strategic planning, linking with EU managed existing data sources (Epidemiological information hosted by ECDC, Population Density from Urban Data Platform, weather data, information on new variants of concern and interest from GISAID etc.) for data input and the visualisation of outputs. (JRC- <https://wastewater-observatory.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#/>).

We contributed to the Member State (Italy) report of data on wastewater surveillance into this system for research and for a homogenised visualisation and decision support for public health authorities.

- III. The EU Wastewater Integrated Surveillance for Public Health (EU-WISH). On 1st of November 2023, the project was started under the Joint Action EU4Health Scheme of the European Commission. The focus of this joint action is to support activities to enhance, extend and consolidate national wastewater surveillance for public health in Member States. In particular, this project aims to improve wastewater surveillance by strengthening knowledge and sharing best practices in order to facilitate the integration of wastewater surveillance with a public health perspective. Moreover, it will support the capability of the European Union Member States for data gathering, information exchange and surveillance, with the objective to protect people in the Union from serious cross-border health threats. The EU-WISH consortium has extensive geographical coverage across Europe, counting on 62

institutes across 26 countries. We participate in the project, as part of the Lombardy Region Wastewater Laboratories Network. The Lombardy Region is an Affiliated Entity to ISS, which participates as partner or Competent Authority.

- IV. ELIXIR COVID19 Wastewater Surveillance Working Group. We contributed to this WG that collaborated with the European Bioinformatics Institute in order to promote the use of the open access databases European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), dedicated to the collection of open access wastewater viral sequencing data. ELIXIR COVID19 Wastewater Surveillance Working Group¹¹).

Viral analysis in a pandemic scenario, concerning different geographic areas and/or communities is dependent on the possibility of analysing standardised data and metadata. Thus, the standardisation of sample collection, transport, preanalytical and analytical processing of samples used for viral detection and characterization is essential.

By contributing to the IDTk section on “Pathogen Characterization - Quality Control” we contributed to the development of standardisation and quality control of wastewater surveillance methods.

- V. The Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk). The Infectious Diseases Toolkit¹² is an evolving platform focused on knowledge exchange and data-driven solutions for infectious disease preparedness.

The IDTk website and GitHub repository <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/pathogen-characterisation/quality-control>; <https://github.com/elixir-europe/infectious-diseases-toolkit> aims to facilitate access, information dissemination, and collaboration. The Ghent Contentathon in March 2023 fostered community growth and new partnerships, while providing an opportunity for the contribution of key knowledge by the community with stakeholders from inside and outside of BY-COVID. During this event a specific section on wastewater surveillance was discussed and developed to be included in the IDTk.

We have actively participated in the development of the IDTk to develop tools and methods and to ensure data quality in wastewater surveillance.

5. Results

The detection, quantification, and sequencing of SARS-CoV-2 viral genomic sequences in wastewater, has shown to enable its use:

- (i) as an early warning system capable of predicting COVID-19 outbreaks in the population days before clinical cases;

¹¹ <https://www.covid19dataportal.org/partners?activeTab=Working%20groups>

¹² <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/>

- (ii) as a tool capable of establishing trends in current outbreaks, including estimates on the prevalence of infections in different geographical areas and assessment on the emergence of SARS-CoV-2 genetic variants;
- (iii) as reliable indicator able to support prevention and management strategies for the containment of pandemic events.

Standardised methods and quality control procedures of wastewater surveillance have been developed to make results of inter-laboratory analysis comparable and applicable on a wider scale. The effectiveness of global coordination and cooperation in fact also depend upon the agreement and implementation of shared international data standards as well as of data systems which are interoperable and compatible.

The Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk) section on “Pathogen Characterization - Quality Control” describes all steps of the dataset creation, starting from the collection of the samples, to the analysis of the data, which should be further documented by provenance. <https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/pathogen-characterisation/quality-control>.

A summary of Sample handling; Preanalytical and analytical methods; NGS pathogens data analysis are presented below.

Sample handling: key for data quality

Quality measures to be adopted from the beginning of the process leading to the detection and characterization of pathogens have been defined, including all pre-analytical and analytical procedures applied to the collection, transport and store of samples, depending on the type of sample. In addition to the procedures, it is key to pay attention to the existing conditions during the different steps of sample collection and processing. Hence, it is important not only to collect relevant information, but also to store it as standardised as possible, to improve interoperability and reusability of the resulting data.

The needed information about sample handling for further data analysis for pathogen surveillance are:

- Geographical area / site of collection and population size served by the wastewater plant from which the sample is being collected.
- Environmental parameters such as rainfall or other environmental aspects or variables that may affect viral target detection and quantification.
- Wastewater sample characteristics: sample volume, 24 hrs composite sample characteristics (m³/24 hrs), grab sample collection or other parameters, such as resuspended solids characteristics (mg/L).

Preanalytical and analytical methods

During the preanalytical and analytical processing of the samples, there are several variables that can potentially affect the data resulting from them (some of them listed below). Thus, following guidelines on the standardisation of methods and keeping track of the chosen procedures are key to get meaningful data from the samples.

For both the pre-analytical and analytical methods, some of the most relevant variables to consider and keep track are:

- sample starting volume;

- pathogen concentration methods / protocols if any;
- extraction methods (protein, DNA, RNA, etc), if any. Keep the information about the devices/technology/kits used, starting volume of sample concentrate, elution volume following extraction, etc;
- hardware/instruments used.
- From the analytical methods:
 - target sequence, if any;
 - analytical methods (ie PCR, qPCR, NGS, etc);
 - information about the enzymes/reagents/kits used (ie. concentrations, volumes, etc.);
 - analytical steps and/or conditions (ie. temperatures, time, number of PCR cycles, etc);
 - hardware/instruments used;

Quality control steps needed for wastewater samples for pathogen surveillance:

- Quality control of the preanalytical process
 - Spiking wastewater samples with exogenous calibrated virus reference material, such as mengovirus or murine norovirus, before preanalytical processing in order to evaluate the efficiency of viral concentration and extraction procedures (by evaluating the recovery of the exogenous reference material introduced into the sample prior to pre-analytical processing).
 - Including a negative control sample during the nucleic acid extraction procedure to evaluate for potential cross contamination.
- Quality control of the quantitative analytical detection
 - Standard calibrated reference material (such as EURM-019 / EURM-014 single stranded RNA provided by the Joint Research Center)

NGS pathogens data analysis

A systematic approach to metadata standardisation and data harmonisation makes it possible to combine and compare datasets, consequently promoting a more universal use and reuse of the data. The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) has put in place some checklists to fill in at data submission for several organism types, an example for pathogen samples can be found here¹³. The metadata describing the sequencing experiment have to be submitted to ENA in an standardised format¹⁴. ENA has set up some standards for SARS-CoV-2. ENA has also standardised checklists for water surveillance.

Further information on wastewater quality control can be found in:

- Wastewater QC workflow in GalaxyTrakr (SSQuAWK3) (protocols.io) protocol that has a nice listing of quality indicators that were defined in the context of SARS-CoV-2, but are easily generalizable.

¹³ <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000033>

¹⁴ <https://ena-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/submit/reads/webin-cli.html#metadata-validation>

- The technical protocol (including analytical methods) of the national SARI project (Surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 in wastewaters in Italy) can be found in <https://zenodo.org/records/5758725>
- The European Commission Recommendation (EU) 2021/472 of 17 March 2021 has advocated the use of a common approach to establish a systematic surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 and its variants in wastewaters in the EU (OJ L 98 19.03.2021, p. 3, CELEX¹⁵). Standards normalisation of wastewater surveillance samples and for PCR/Digital-PCR (polymerase chain reaction) and Next Generation Sequence are indicated in this Recommendation document.

¹⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021H0472>

Summary Table linking the contribution of the deliverable to the objectives

Objective	Description	Link to the source(s)
Obj 1.2	Open-source workflows and processing pipelines integrating quality management and provenance	https://doi.org/10.3390/w14050833 https://www.infectious-diseases-toolkit.org/pathogen-characterisation/quality-control
Obj 1.4	Engagement to stakeholders incorporate FAIR and open data infectious disease guidelines	https://www.iss.it/cov19-acque-reflue-ELIXIR-COVID19-Wastewater-Surveillance-Working-Group
Obj 2.3	Demonstrate transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries, that allow the assessment of variants (...)	https://www.iss.it/cov19-acque-reflue https://wastewater-observatory.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#/ https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/ERC000033
Obj 5.2	Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects openly accessible for reuse.	Infectious Diseases Toolkit (IDTk) https://github.com/elixir-europe/infectious-diseases-toolkit https://zenodo.org/records/5758725

6. Discussion

In pandemic research, the development of an effective surveillance system is necessary for the preparedness leading to the application of preventive or therapeutic measures.

During the early phases of the COVID-19 pandemic event, traditional clinical surveillance systems were found to be inadequate to assess its spread. This was partly the result of limited availability of diagnostic tests with hospitalisation representing only a measure of symptomatic infections.

Early into COVID-19 pandemic, the demonstration of faecal shedding of SARS-CoV2 by infected individuals, both symptomatic and asymptomatic, allowed to document the presence of SARS-CoV2 RNA in wastewater. The detection of the virus RNA in sewage, even at times of low COVID-19 prevalence, and the correlation between viral concentrations in sewage and reported prevalence of COVID-19, indicated that sewage surveillance could be a sensitive tool to monitor the circulation of the virus in the population.

Detecting and quantifying genomic sequences of emerging pathogens associated with pandemic events in wastewater provides a low cost, community-representative sample, unbiased by the presence or absence of symptoms, access to diagnostic tests and/or hospitalisation. However, methods optimization and quality control are crucial for generating reliable public health information among countries and over time.

By participating in national and European initiatives we contributed

- to the collection and reporting of wastewater epidemiology data in a timely manner through national and European dedicated dashboards and/or websites;
- to the identification of needs in the standardisation and harmonisation of laboratory methods and metadata in order to provide interoperability of data and information exchange across borders to drive public health measures;
- to connect by bridging and contributing to several European initiatives on wastewater surveillance as a tool for improved preparedness for present and future public health threats.

We also evaluated the performance of different pre-analytical and analytical methods for identifying the presence of SARS-CoV-2 in untreated municipal wastewaters samples and collaborated to develop a common protocol of analysis by optimising and standardising the methods for the pre-analytical and analytical workflow in order to make results of inter-laboratory analysis comparable and applicable on a wider scale.

Our work demonstrated the utility and importance of the implementation and exploitation of harmonised protocols and methods for the detection in real time of circulating pathogens in geographical epidemic ‘hotspots’ for an effective pandemic preparedness surveillance system.

Data from epidemic ‘hotspots’, connected with other data in relevant databases, offer a better understanding.

7. Conclusions

We have delivered use cases on hot spots detection through the collection and report of wastewater epidemiology data through national and European dedicated dashboards and/or websites showing the workflow components.

The data are available in the open domain, allowing access and further studies.

In collaboration with WP4 we also developed the Infectious Diseases Toolkit to ensure that data quality in wastewater surveillance covers all steps of the dataset creation, starting from sample collection, through to analysis of data. Further work is needed to standardise quality control procedures and harmonise datasets generated from different sources so that they can be grouped and/or compared across countries.

8. Next steps

The following steps are planned for the work described here:

- Continue to collect and report wastewater epidemiology data through national and European dedicated dashboards and/or websites

- Promote the interoperability of methods for sampling and analysis at a European level and the harmonisation of open-access metadata collection and standardisation, allowing to promote its use in driving public health preparedness and implementation of disease control measures.
- Promote bridges to wastewater surveillance projects: EU Sewage Sentinel System for SARS-CoV-2 and the Digital European Exchange Platform (EU4S-DEEP), coordinated by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC-<https://wastewater-observatory.jrc.ec.europa.eu/#/>); EU Wastewater Integrated Surveillance for Public Health (EU-WISH) project in the frame of the Joint Action EU4Health Scheme.
- Link COVID-19 Data Portal to all other repositories of wastewater surveillance data.

9. Impact

With this work, we studied the implementation and exploitation of wastewater-based surveillance systems to provide an important predictive model for the early detection of epidemic hotspots.

Models based on wastewater surveillance, including covariates such as COVID-19 vaccine coverage, comorbidities, demographic variables, and holiday gatherings, have been shown to have higher predictive power than models that included clinical cases only^{8,9}.

Such study is important in preparedness for future pandemics to enable fast-track use of wastewater-based surveillance open data and data sharing to drive public health initiatives aimed at implementing timely intervention strategies/measures to contain infections outbreaks/circulation of new viral variants, such as in the case of SARS-CoV2.

The work highlighted that a successful surveillance strategy for pandemic preparedness will also need:

- to combine national, regional, and global data in a way that is fast, accurate, and globally coordinated and connected;
- to agree and to implement shared international data standards as well as of data systems which are interoperable and compatible;
- to identify public domain repositories;
- to develop digital tools, novel models of analysis, such as those including machine learning and artificial intelligence, and informatics resources.⁴

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